

Feed conversion ratio (FCR) and nutrient retention in aquafeed using clover as a protein source: a study on kingfish, *Seriola lalandi*

Problem

EU aquaculture relies on fishmeal and imported soy, driving additional pressure on the environment and the climate. A local and more sustainable source of protein must be identified.

Solution

The quality of novel aquafeed ingredients, such as forage legumes, can be assessed based on nutrient utilisation by the target fish species. This can be evaluated through controlled feeding and digestibility trials conducted year-round in recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS).

Benefits

The use of locally grown forage legumes in aquafeeds can improve farm profitability, enhance European protein self-sufficiency, create more stable markets, and incentivise the expansion of legume cultivation.

Practical recommendations

- Clover concentrates can have high protein levels ($\geq 58\%$) and can be suitable protein sources in aquafeeds for fish species.
- Feeding experiments can provide insight into the quality of a feed or ingredient, in terms of nutrient retention and feed conversion. In this study, a protein concentrate made from clover and grass (CG) (58% protein; commercial product from Vestjyllands Andel A.m.b.a, Denmark) was tested for kingfish (*Seriola lalandi* Valenciennes, 1833) diets.
- **Nutrient retention** Decreases with inclusion of 30 % CG in diets. The apparent digestibility coefficient (ADC) of crude protein is 82 % (for fishmeal diet: 91%). The ADC of CG is 68 %.
- The **FCR** is best with a CG inclusion of up to 10% in diets, indicating that kingfish maintain an acceptable feed efficiency at this inclusion level (**Fig. 1**).

Applicability box

Theme

Applications of a forage legume (clover) in fish feed for Kingfish.

Keywords

Clover *Trifolium*, protein source, fish feed, nutrient retention, feed conversion ratio.

Context

Europe.

Application time

All year round in RAS.

Required time

Duration of feeding trials plus digestibility analyses (approx. 5 - 7 month).

Period of impact

Application in juvenile fish (20 - 300 g).

Equipment

RAS, Equipment for feed production.

Best in

Applicable in RAS on the target fish species.

Figure 1. Feed conversion ratio (FCR) of the kingfish fed the experimental diets with increasing CG content (0 to 35 %) and reduced soy protein concentrate and fishmeal content. Com = Commercial kingfish diet.

- Dietary inclusion of CG induces an increase in **skin greenness**. This suggests that compounds within CG influence pigment deposition or expression in the skin of this species (**Fig. 2**).

Figure 2 Shows kingfish fed with diets containing increasing CG content, from left to right (Vanessa Fuchs).

Further information

Further reading

- Bellof, G. and Freitag, M. (eds) (2025) *Legumes in livestock and fish nutrition: Ingredients, feed value and feeding recommendations*. Leiden: Brill. DOI: 10.3920/9789004695047

About this practice abstract

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